

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3724558
CZU 378.146/.147:81

MONITORING ASSIMILATION AND ASSESSMENT OF STUDENT KNOWLEDGE

Ala Șișianu*, ORCID: ID 0000-0002-3259-5681

Technical University of Moldova, 168, Stefan cel Mare bd., Chisinau, Republic of Moldova
*ala.sisianu@ia.utm.md

Received: 12.18.2019

Accepted: 02.28.2020

Abstract. The article is an attempt to collect and present some of the methods and techniques used daily in the didactic process of teaching. The students should be motivated to not only study and obtain pretty good result, but to analyze, to estimate and assess the knowledge they gained and to try to evaluate the results of their group mates. It will increase the students' self-esteem, their attitude and responsibility towards the classes and tests, towards different projects, mutual collaboration and even the attitude on the way to exams.

Keywords: *assessment, technique, method, teaching and learning process, improvement, knowledge, exam.*

Rezumat. Articolul este o încercare de a colecta și prezenta unele dintre metodele și tehnicile utilizate zilnic în procesul didactic de predare a limbilor moderne. Studenții ar trebui să fie motivați nu numai să studieze și să obțină rezultate destul de bune, ci și să analizeze, să estimeze și să evalueze cunoștințele dobândite și să încerce să evalueze rezultatele colegilor de grup. Acesta va crește respectul de sine al studenților, atitudinea și responsabilitatea lor față de cursuri și teste, față de diferite proiecte, propuse de profesor, colaborare reciprocă și chiar atitudinea față de examene.

Cuvinte cheie: *evaluare, tehnică, metodă, proces de predare și învățare, îmbunătățire, cunoștințe, examen.*

Introduction

The process of education is a complex structure of teaching, learning and assessing the material included in curricula. At the same time, it is a live process when we, as teachers, as advisors should not just provide the taught material as a product but monitor the material assimilation as we do prepare future specialists, who will have to use their gained knowledge in practice, will apply it while working, while creating/producing something.

Therefore, we must be sure that every lesson was not just a pleasant spending of time but a useful improving or developing activity. Each teacher has his own techniques [1, p. 28], which make the teaching-studying process more effective. So do I, and in this very article I want to share some of the methods I use.

“Flash”- testing of the current lesson material

Usually, at the end of the lesson, teachers provide monitoring of the material assimilation by an oral survey of two, three or even four students. A more effective method is to apply a written “flash” testing within 5 - 10 minutes. This will increase the reliability of the quality of assimilated material [5, p. 112].

To increase the activity or just the students’ attentiveness, the teacher should warn students about the “flash” testing at the beginning of the lesson. This will make them take the lesson more seriously, especially if they are informed that they will be graded or simply said will be marked. It is advisable to give such “flashes” on the most important educational material, but not often, so that their unusualness and severity do not disappear.

The motivation of students to self-assess the degree of perception

Teachers quite rarely use this interesting, original and effective technique, mostly because it requires additional time. Its essence is as follows. After three or four classes with a new audience, the teacher asks students to make “informative” notes on the margins of their copybooks. It is mostly because the feedback between teacher and students is insufficient, and it is not always clear how students have learned this or that material, and the other reason is to identify how to teach them further.

If students have learned the material well, they have to put 1 in the margin; if the material is not entirely clear - 2; if the material is interesting and they want to know more about it - 3. The teacher will periodically review students’ notes, which will be a kind of guideline on what more attention to pay to, what changes to do, etc.

It turns out that such a request does not cause any opposition from the students [3, p. 44]. Moreover, as it turned out, the majority of the students willingly work in the classroom; it implies more activities, they have to evaluate what the teacher said, analyze, think; there is no time to be distracted.

The information received by the teacher is very large. Firstly, it promotes active record keeping (after all, the teacher will periodically review them); secondly, it is possible to judge by the records of the integrity and activity of a student; thirdly, a fairly deep, although not entirely operational, feedback is carried out. Obviously, the teacher needs periodically to review the student notes. Apparently, this is precisely what inhibits the use of the considered technique.

“For” - “Against” - “Abstained”

Very often, with the current control of the material assimilation, when solving problem situations, during the lesson, etc., the students have opposite opinions or decisions on a particular issue.

The teacher, having formulated one of the opinions, conducts a vote (by show of hands), finding out who agrees with this opinion (“for”), who does not agree (“against”), and who finds it difficult to answer (“abstained”).

The results of such voting can serve as one of the feedback methods. At the same time, voting increases the activity of students, since it requires the participation of all students, each of whom tries to answer the question correctly, even to guess the answer. In addition, a special, democratic environment is created, which is, as it were, an emotional discharge.

The effect of admission is significantly increased when students find out that their opinion really counts.

“Think and Decide (Answer)”

The technique refers to the category of long-term ones. Before starting to study a new topic or section, the students are given a list of questions, tasks, for which, in addition to knowledge of the educational material, they should include their insight, intuition, creativity, non-standard thinking. It is better to print and deliver the texts of these questions, tasks for students to see and use them any time they need and want to [7, p. 121]. The students are informed that one of the first who correctly completes the task will benefit of moral incentive measures, for example, exemption from certain types of reporting.

Knowledge control

This procedure is effective when used regularly. Its essence is that checking the quality of mastering the knowledge of students at the beginning of the lesson, on previously studied material, or at the end of it, based on the material of the current lesson is delegated to one of the students.

It is advisable to inform all trainees about this in advance, at first - it is possible even to notice each name for them to be clear that the process is for the whole group and is a serious one [2, p. 76].

The person in charge announces his results to the students while the teacher sets the final assessments. Assessment of the responsible for the lesson evaluation is given by the teacher taking into account the knowledge of the material, his ability to formulate questions correctly, the coincidence of his students' knowledge assessment with the assessments of the teacher.

In addition to the increasing interest and activity of students caused by the preparation for the control of knowledge, the technique positively affects such qualities of a future specialist as improving methodological skills and objectivity in evaluating the activities of subordinates.

In order to make the method really “work”, a certain training of the students is required. They must firstly be familiarized with the basics of the methodology for guiding the proper knowledge control, trained in formulating questions correctly, etc. It is advisable to do this out of the class, not at the proper lesson, but before, for example at a consultation or tutoring meetings.

Material Reduction for the Exam

In the course of the semester, some teachers practice giving tests to the students on specific topics, sections or units of the discipline. During the exam, students do not report/are not re-asked on that material.

This allows, when using the technique, firstly, to some extent relieve the atmosphere of the exam, and reduce the tension throughout the exam session. Secondly, and this is the most important thing, the students at an objectively high level sustain the received knowledge throughout the semester. Instead of giving the proper test, you can give those who wish a special task: prepare an essay, explore or make a survey on a certain topic, etc. After a successful accomplishment of the task, a certain material submitted for examination is also reduced.

Practice has shown that the number of students who want to “settle accounts” with the exam during the semester or significantly facilitate during the examination session is about 15–25%.

Knowledge self- and mutual assessment

Before starting to study the academic discipline for which an examination (test) is provided, the teacher has to inform the students that on the eve of the exam they must evaluate their knowledge (for example, on a five-point system), the marks will be compared with the marks obtained as a result of the exam. Raising up of students' activities consists in trying to prepare better for the exam, in developing a sense of self-criticism and objectivity in assessing their knowledge, since the teacher can negatively perceive students' self-esteem overestimating or understating [4, p. 54]. Our technique can be used not only with references to exams, but also in assessing the degree of preparation for laboratory works, the quality of some written papers, etc. It is possible to use the so-called mutual assessing and evaluate students' knowledge by group mates [5, p. 89], that is, when the knowledge of each student is proposed to be assessed by one or two students of their choice or on the recommendation of their teacher.

Open knowledge sheet

This is quite a common procedure for our teachers. Most of us use it daily during the academic year. The study group gets a statement of accounting grades for the discipline. All grades/marks are given and noted in the teacher's "register" for the answers from the place, for an interesting question or answer, increased activity, attentiveness, accuracy in the classroom, results within "Flash" tests, fluent verbal interviews, etc. The teacher regularly announces the results a student gained, for him to know what should be done to improve the results and his own process of studying [8, p. 23]. The general review, visibility, and comparability of the assessments of all students affect the feeling of healthy self-esteem, increase motivation and desire for activity, especially if the students know that the teacher will take the data from the "register" into account during the final control of knowledge.

Conclusion

There are a lot of efficient methods and techniques to brush up the learning and studying processes. A lot is done in order to motivate the students' interest in obtaining not only good results but also powerful and long lasting knowledge. We, as tutors and advisors, as those who plant the seeds of science in those who come to study led by the best teachers, continuously try to improve the academic process and ourselves. Very often we, due to the great work experience know much more than we do think. Why not to share the methods we use with those who need and want to make their work more qualified. In the very article, I tried to present some of the teachers' "tricks" I use. They are tested by time and I consider them quite efficient. The list for sure could be continued and enlarged. There is always place for something new.

References

1. Abdullina O.L. General pedagogical training in the system of higher pedagogical staff. M., 1984 (In Russian).
2. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya K.A. Life strategy. M., 1991 (In Russian).
3. Azarov Yu.P. The Art of Education: A book for the teacher. M., 1985 (In Russian).
4. Kuznetsov I.N. Handbook of a practicing teacher. M., 2000.
5. W. K. Kellogg Foundation. (1998). Evaluation handbook. Retrieved from <http://www.wkcf.org/Pubs/Tools/Evaluation/Pub770.pdf>
6. Lang James M. Small teaching: Everyday Lessons from the Science of Learning. Jossey-Bass, US, 2016.
7. Michelle D. Miller's Minds Online: Teaching Effectively With Technology (Harvard, 2016).
8. Wholey, J. S., Hatry, H. P., & Newcomer, K. E. (1994). Handbook of practical program evaluation. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.